

AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF LOW VELOCITY IMPACT ON CARBON, GLASS AND MIXED FIBER COMPOSITE PLATES

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ABSTRACT

One of the problem with composites is their poor impact damage resistance and low post-impact mechanical properties. Composites are prone to delamination damage when impacted by low speed projectiles because of the poor through-thickness strength. . To combat the problem of delamination damage, composite parts are often over-designed with extra thickness. However, this increases the cost, weight and volume of the composite and in some cases may provide only moderate improvements to impact damage resistance. The selection of the optimum parameters for composite plates that give high impact resistance under low velocity impact loads should consider several factors related to the materials properties as well as to the way of manufacturing of the composite product. To get the desired impact resistance, it is essential to know interrelationships between these parameters and the absorbed energy by the plate or the pipe. The process of developing this relationship is not an easy task because there are some unknown, nonlinear process parameters. Knowing which parameters have an effect on the improvement on the composite impact resistance and which parameters give the most significant effect are the main issues in composite industry. In this work, impact response of composite laminates was experimentally studied with drop-tower Instron 9250G to determine the energy absorption. Three types of composites were used: carbon fiber, glass fiber and mixed fiber composite laminates. In addition, these composites were characterized by different stacking sequences and resin types. Impact loads were applied at the center of each plate with a dimensions of 129 mm by 129 mm. The effect of several composite structural parameters on the absorbed energy of composite plates is studied.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced composite polymer are used in almost all types of advanced engineering structures. They combine glass or carbon reinforcing fibers with a matrix material such as epoxy, phenolic, or polyester. Composite materials are complex, mainly due to the degree of anisotropy induced by the reinforcing fibers. Thermosetting polymers consist of chain molecules that chemically bond or cross-link with the other when heated together. Composite materials have a high resistance to internal and external corrosion. They are light with a very smooth inside for higher throughputs.

Manufacturing a composite structure starts by incorporating a large number of fibers in a thin layer of matrix to form a ply. The required load in a fiber reinforced composite structure is obtained by stacking a plurality of layers in a specified order and then group to form a ply. Various layers in a ply can contain fibers in different directions. It is also possible to combine different types of fibers (for example glass and carbon) to form a hybrid laminate.

Low velocity impact by foreign objects is a major concern for composite laminate as this impact can cause damage to the interior of materials, which significantly reduces the strength of the composite component and it may not be easily detected. The complexity of such impact on composite laminate is due to the different failure modes that occur in composites compared with metals.

The selection of optimal parameters for composite plates that give high resistance to low velocity impact loads should consider various factors related to material properties, as well as the manner of manufacturing of the composite product. To obtain the desired impact resistance, it is essential to know the correlation between these parameters and the energy absorbed by the composite plate. The

development process of this correlation is not an easy task because unknown process parameters are nonlinear. Knowing the parameters affecting the impact resistance and the degree to which these parameters affect are the most significant problems of the composite laminate industry.

Drop weight impact testing is the common test procedure used to study the impact resistance and the behavior of composite laminates. Drop weight testing also tends to be the preferred method when performing low velocity impact testing. ASTM Test Method D7136/D7136M [3] is the governed international standard used to study the impact testing on a rectangular plate. This test method determines the damage resistance of multidirectional polymer matrix composite laminated plates subjected to a drop-weight impact event. The standard test utilizes a constant impact energy normalized by specimen thickness. The properties obtained using this test method can provide guidance in regard to the anticipated damage resistance of composite structures of similar material, thickness, stacking sequence, and so forth. To compare samples in a quantitative manner, several equations may be used, which can be found in ASTM D7136.

Hosur et al. [2] carried out experimental investigations to determine the response of four different combinations of hybrid laminates to low-velocity impact loading using an instrumented impact testing machine. Their study indicated that there is considerable improvement in the load carrying capability of hybrid composites as compared to carbon or epoxy laminates with slight reduction in stiffness.

Yang & Cantwell [8] conducted a number of low velocity impact tests on (0° , 90°) glass fiber reinforced epoxy resin to study the effects of varying key parameters on the damage initiation threshold. The results show that the impact resistance is proportional to the thickness of the composite panel. Also, the tests show that the impact resistance was not affected by the plate's geometry. A further study by Yang et al. [8] was done to study the as target size, projectile diameter and test temperature on damage initiation. The tests were carried out on samples of unidirectional E-glass fiber reinforced FM94 epoxy resin. The majority of tests were conducted on laminates of 1.8 mm thickness while few tests were carried out on laminates of thickness ranging from 0.8 mm to 3.6 mm. Tests were also undertaken to study the effect of temperature on the damage initiation. Tests were carried out at temperatures of 45° , 60° , 75° and 90° C. In these tests, the damage initiation threshold was established by increasing the impact energy until delamination just became apparent in the test samples. The samples were not subjected to multiple impact tests considering that would result in fatigue and a lower value of damage threshold. The tests conducted by Yang and Cantwell [8] suggested that the damage initiation force is proportional to the target thickness. The tests demonstrated dependency in the order of $t^{3/2}$, where "t" is the thickness of the composite plate. This result was verified with the studies conducted earlier. They also carried out experimental studies on whether the geometry of the test specimen affects the damage initiation threshold. This result was also supported by earlier studies that the damage initiation threshold does not depend upon the panel size. The final parameter studied was the effect of temperature and several tests were conducted at a number of temperatures between 23° and 90° C. A linear relationship was observed between the thickness of the panel and the damage initiation force at a particular temperature. It was observed that the damage threshold increased with temperature for thinner laminates.

Keršys, Keršienė, & Žiliukas [6] studied the impact response of woven carbon/epoxy and E-Glass/epoxy composite systems on vehicle body structures by considering energy profile diagrams and force-displacement curves. To determine the mechanism of impact damage, drop-weight experiments were performed when laminated composite materials were deformed with low impact energy. The maximum energy used in the test was equal to 120J by means of a vertically falling impactor. The total amount of energy introduced to a composite specimen and the energy absorbed by the composite specimen through the impact event are important parameters to assess impact response of the composite structures. The experiments demonstrated a reduction in the stiffness of the composite plate.

Rilo & Ferreira [7] conducted study on the experimental investigation of low velocity impacts on glass-epoxy laminated composite plates. The characterization of the damage was done in relation to the type of test, stacking sequence, dimensions and the maximum force of the impact.

Many useful techniques have been successfully devised to improve the delamination resistance in the past three decades, namely three-dimensional (3D)-weaving, stitching, braiding, embroidery, Z-pin anchoring, fiber hybridization, toughening the matrix resin and interleaving with tough polymer, short fibers or micro-scale particles. These methods enhanced the interlaminar properties but at the cost of in-plane mechanical properties [1].

Analysis of absorbed energy and velocities during impact testing of composites may not be all that is needed for characterization. For damage mechanism characterization and type of failure identification, post-impact analysis is required to be carried out for the damaged sample [4]. Visual inspection can be used to analyze the impact tested samples for specific damage types that include dent/depression, cracking/ splitting, fiber failure, and delamination.

The behavior of low velocity impact on the composites has been comprehensively studied by others in the technical literature. However, the aim of the current work is to investigate impact response of the angle-ply laminated plates using different fibers (carbon and glass). Combination of two types of fibers will be also tried. Several type of stacking sequences and resins will be considered. Absorbed energy-time curves will be presented to understand the behavior of the low impact velocity loading.

2 EXPERIMENTAL TESTS

2.1 MATERIALS AND SPECIMEN MANUFACTURING

The materials in this study consist of carbon, glass and mixed fiber-reinforced laminates which were manufactured with a symmetric, quasi-isotropic lay-up of plies. Different ply thickness and resin types were also considered. Table 1 summarizes the detailed information for the 19 symmetric laminated composite plates that were impact tested. These composites were characterized by different stacking sequences. The amount of fiber and resin for each specimen was also considered with different ratio as shown in Table 1. Note that C stands for carbon-fiber, G stands for glass-fiber and M stands for mixed-fiber. For matrix material, three types of resins were used which are epoxy, phenolic (PH) and polyester (PL). The final size of each test specimen is 129 mm X 129 mm.

Table 1: Composite Laminates' Properties

No.	Sample No.	Materials Type	Glue Type (Resin)	Percentage of Fiber	Percentage of Epoxy	No. of Layers	Stacking Sequence	Measured thickness (mm)
1	C1	Carbon	Epoxy	42.48	57.52	16	[90/-60/-30/0/90/-60/-30/0]s	3.3
2	C2	Carbon	Epoxy	43.59	56.41	16	[90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	3.8
3	C3	Carbon	Epoxy	45.49	54.51	20	[45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	4.7
4	C4	Carbon	Epoxy	45.74	54.26	24	[90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	5.5
5	C4 PH	Carbon	Phenolic	45.74	54.26	24	[90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	5.15
6	C4 PL	Carbon	Polyester	45.74	54.26	24	[90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	5.5
7	C5	Carbon	Epoxy	47.68	52.32	28	[45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	6.4
8	C6	Carbon	Epoxy	47.58	52.42	32	[90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	7.4
9	C7	Carbon	Epoxy	45.52	54.48	28	[-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60]s	6.6
10	C8	Carbon	Epoxy	50.00	50.00	32	[60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60]s	7.3
11	G1	Glass	Epoxy	50.04	49.96	24	[90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	4.9
12	G1 PH	Glass	Phenolic	50.04	49.96	24	[90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	5
13	G1 PL	Glass	Polyester	50.04	49.96	24	[90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	4.7
14	G4	Glass	Epoxy	52.51	47.49	24	[90/-60/-30/0/90/-60/-30/0/90/-60/-30/0]s	5.1
15	G5	Glass	Epoxy	58.79	41.21	36	[-30/-45/45/30/-30/-45/45/30/-30/-45/45/30/-30/-45/45/30/-30/-45/45/30/-30/-45]s	7.1
16	G6	Glass	Epoxy	66.60	33.40	36	[45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	7.4
17	M1	Mixed Carbon-Glass (2 C in the Middle)	Epoxy	62.50	37.50	32	[60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60]s	6.5
18	M2	Mixed Carbon-Glass (2	Epoxy	62.53	37.47	32	[60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60]s	6.7

		C in the Bottom)						
19	M3	Mixed Carbon-Glass (2 C in the Top)	Epoxy	64.51	35.49	32	[60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60]s	6.7

2.2 LOW VELOCITY IMPACT TESTING

The low velocity impact tests were performed by a drop tower “INSTRON Dynatup 9250G”. The equipment consists of striker holder which accommodates additional weights, striker and hemispherical impactor. The impact machine was equipped with a hemispherical impactor head with diameter of 1 inch.

Weights are added to alter the energy of the impact. For all impact tests in this study, the mass of the impactor was 9.2 kg with constant impact energy level of 20 J and corresponding to an impact velocity of 2.06 m/s. The impact velocity is measured by a photocell device that is placed in the path of the striker before the impactor strikes the composite plates. The force-time history is measured from the point of initial contact with the plate until the impactor travels through the composite plate thickness. The energy is calculated from the integration of the force-time signal. The force-time history and energy-time were recorded by the data acquisition system. For impact conditions in which the striker recovered from the composite plate, multiple impacts may occur causing excessive damage, which is not desirable. To avoid such repeated impacts, two rebound arrestors are located on both sides of the composite plate. The arrestors are pneumatically actuated rebound, and spring up and separate the impactor from the composite plate after the first impact. Figure 1 shows the schematic picture of the drop weight machine.

Figure 1: Schematic of drop weight machine

The composite plates to be impacted was positioned under the drop tower using an in-house manufactured specimen fixture where the exposed composite area within the fixture is 110 mm X 110 mm. The composite plates were clamped along all edges. Clamping force is provided by steel plates on the top and bottom edges as shown in the schematic drawing (Figure 2). The clamping force is applied by tightening 2 bolts at edge of the fixture.

Figure 2: Schematic view of the fixture and sample location within the fixture

Various properties can be obtained from low velocity impact tests which includes impact velocity and incipient energy (E_i), total energy absorbed (E_t), total deflection (I_t), incipient damage point (P_i), maximum load (P_{max}), failure load point, total load point (P_t), energy at maximum load (E_m), deflection at maximum load (I_m) and energy ($E_p = E_t - E_m$) and deflection ($I_p = I_t - I_m$) after maximum load as shown in Figure 3 [9].

Figure 3: Typical Load and Energy Verses time curve and characteristic points for post impact analysis [9]

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As per the procedure described above a total of 19 impact testing were performed using INSTRON Dynatup 9250G drop tower in order to determine the amount of impact energy lost in damage during the impact process for each of the defined cases per Table-2.

Table 2: Low velocity impact properties of composite samples

Sample No.	No. of Layers	Stacking Sequence	Measured thickness (mm)	Peak Load (kN)	Deflection at Peak Load (mm)	Energy to max load (J)	Total energy (J)	Energy to failure (J)
C1	16	[90/-60/-30/0/90/-60/-30/0] _s	3.3	4.48	4.97	14.65	15.68	16.21

Sample No.	No. of Layers	Stacking Sequence	Measured thickness (mm)	Peak Load (kN)	Deflection at Peak Load (mm)	Energy to max load (J)	Total energy (J)	Energy to failure (J)
C2	16	[90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	3.8	4.10	4.69	13.27	16.27	16.80
C3	20	[45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	4.7	5.83	4.67	19.50	14.25	14.78
C4	24	[90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	5.5	7.66	3.42	16.51	12.75	13.36
C4 PH	24	[90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	5.15	5.62	6.63	20.33	13.78	14.68
C4 PL	24	[90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	5.5	8.34	4.16	19.64	11.18	11.93
C5	28	[45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	6.4	9.57	3.03	18.06	12.89	13.41
C6	32	[90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	7.4	11.25	2.68	18.50	10.69	11.32
C7	28	[-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60]s	6.6	9.45	3.18	19.13	12.62	13.19
C8	32	[60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60]s	7.3	11.44	2.73	19.73	14.16	11.23
G1	24	[90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	4.9	7.59	4.90	20.04	9.01	9.89
G1 PH	24	[90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	5	5.53	7.47	18.84	13.20	14.35
G1 PL	24	[90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	4.7	7.57	4.97	20.36	9.49	10.30
G4	24	[90/-60/-30/0/90/-60/-30/0/90/-60/-30/0]s	5.1	7.45	4.76	20.06	10.22	10.96
G5	36	[-30/-45/45/30/-30/-45/45/30/-30/-45/45/30/-30/-45/45/30/-30/-45]s	7.1	10.09	3.24	19.99	9.46	10.25
G6	36	[45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45]s	7.4	9.66	3.19	19.77	11.08	11.73
M1	32	[60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60]s	6.5	9.66	3.19	19.77	11.08	11.73
M2	32	[60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60]s	6.7	8.74	3.53	20.05	11.51	12.16
M3	32	[60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60/60/45/-45/-60]s	6.7	8.91	3.47	19.34	11.28	11.94

Figure 4 summarizes the measured absorbed energies per unit thickness for all composite samples where carbon-fiber composite sample C1 exhibits the highest absorbed energy.

Figure 4: Summary of the measured absorbed energy for all composite plates

Time versus impact energy plots are shown in Figures. 5, 6 and 8 for carbon-fiber, glass-fiber and mixed-fiber composites respectively, where the time history of the kinetic energy of the impactor is shown. In these curves, the highest peak of the curve shows the maximum impact energy and the end of the curve shows the absorbed energy. The (maximum impact) initial kinetic energy is approximately 20 J, and as the impactor contacts the plate, part of the energy is transferred to the plate. At the end of the impact, not all of the initial kinetic energy is returned to the impactor as part of it is absorbed by processes like plastic deformation and failure of the composite plate. The results indicate that there is a large dependence of the impact performance of composite plates on some parameters such as the thickness of the layer, number of layers and stacking sequence.

For carbon fiber composite plate, the tests show that the impact resistance was affected by the plate's thickness and the number of plies. It was found that the behavior of the carbon-fiber/epoxy plates was initially peculiar as the absorbed energy reduced with an increase in the thickness, therefore, improving the performance of the composite plates against the low velocity impact loads. However, a further increase in the overall thickness of the plate either by means of increase in layer thickness or by increasing the number of layers resulted in the decrease in performance. This behavior is strange and was not observed in glass-fiber/epoxy system. This behavior is clearly seen for all the different cases of stacking sequence.

Physically, this phenomenon can be explained such that when the thickness of the composite plate is small, the plate behaves much more like a membrane and during impact the plate stretches until all the kinetic energy is transferred to the plate and then it pushes back the impactor giving away some of the energy back to the impactor and the rest is dissipated in the form of damage within the plate. The more the thickness of the plate is increased, the stiffer it gets and the ability to bend under impact loads is reduced which increases the bending stress and hence the plate suffers more damage. At very high thickness, the plate becomes very strong which results in very low amounts of energy absorbed.

Moreover, absorbed energy in the carbon composites changed with the change in stacking sequence due to the stress redistribution within the laminate. The results show that the minimum amount of energy absorbed is for the case where the laminate configuration is such that the laminate behaves as quasi-isotropic material.

The number of layers does not show a linear relation like the stacking sequence. Increasing and decreasing the number of layers by 5% while keeping the total laminate thickness constant result in increased impact energy absorption. Hence, it can be deduced that there must be an optimal number of layers for a fixed thickness which will give the better impact performance. Thus, there must be an optimum condition for which the amount of absorbed energy and the resulting damage will be minimum.

The results from this experimental work (Figures 5 and 6) show that the carbon-fiber/epoxy composite plate has better impact resistance compared to glass-fiber/epoxy composite plate due to the higher measured strength and the fracture energies of the carbon-fiber/epoxy. C1 has the highest measured absorbed energy then C2, C3, C4 PH, C4, C5, C4 PL, C7 while C6 has the lowest absorbed energy. It worth mentioning that there almost negligible differences in the measured absorbed energy for C5, C4 PL and C7.

Figure 5: Absorbed energy history of low velocity impact for different carbon fiber epoxy plates

Figure 6 shows the measured absorbed energy per unit thickness and it was found that G1 PH has the highest measured absorbed energy then G1 PL, G4, G1, G6 while G5 has the lowest absorbed energy.

It was expected that the composite plates with glass fiber as the reinforcement material will behave in a similar fashion as the carbon fiber based plates. However, we noticed that the effect of thickness of individual layers show that the increase in thickness results in the increase in the absorbed energy and the effect of thickness is most profound on the impact performance of the composite plate. In addition, a higher energy absorption is clearly seen in [45/-45/90/0]s composite plates than other composite plates' stacking sequences.

Figure 6: Absorbed energy for different glass fiber epoxy plates

Delamination, crack or indentation are normally the observed damage forms. Figure 7 shows the extent of damage for the glass fiber composite samples (G1, G4, G5 and G6) from front and back sides. We can correlate the extent of the damage with the measured absorbed energy where we can conclude that the higher absorbed energy shows less damage as in the case of G4.

Figure 7: Glass fiber epoxy plates, (Top: front side, Bottom: back side)

To understand the relation between the placement of the inclusions and the impact performance, different placements were tried for the carbon layers in the composite plate that mainly consisted of glass fibers. The inclusion of other materials alone cannot guarantee a better performance of the structure and the placement of the carbon fibers is equally critical. Since, the material to be included is based on the superior strength and better performance, it should be placed where the damage initiates. Following different combinations were tried with the position of woven carbon lamina as:

- Middle 2 layers
- Bottom 2 layers
- Top 2 layers

For the above mentioned mixed composite combination, the glass fiber composite with 2 carbon fiber plies on the bottom has the highest value of the absorbed energy in compression with the same plate with carbon fiber plies on the middle or in the top. However, the difference is not that pronounced as can be seen from Figure 8.

Figure 8: Absorbed energy for different mixed (glass/carbon) fiber epoxy plates

An interesting result was obtained for absorbed energy-time given in Figures. 9 & 10 for glass and carbon fibers' plates respectively using different types of resin. It was found that the plate with phenolic resin gives the highest absorbed energy when it is compared with the epoxy and polyester resin for both glass and carbon composite plates.

Figure 9: Absorbed energy for different glass fiber plates using different resins

Figure 10: Absorbed energy for different carbon fiber plates using different resins

Figure 11 shows the surface of the glass fiber composite plates with different resins (epoxy, polyester and phenolic) that was tested at the same energy levels. The pictures reveals that the plate with phenolic resin shows minimal damage in both top and bottom side of the plates. The damage of the glass

fiber with epoxy and PL resins samples are clearly observed on both side of the plate. It is also observed that the damage distribution is much larger in the glass fiber plate with polyester resin than in the glass fiber epoxy plate.

Figure 11: Glass fiber plates with different resins (top: front side, bottom: back side)

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the low velocity impact behavior of laminated carbon, glass and mixed fiber plates with different types of resins was investigated. The results presented in the current study gives an insight into the effects of the considered parameters on the impact resistance performance. The amount of energy absorbed varies significantly for the variations in the thickness of a single layer, number of layers and stacking sequence. Several type of stacking sequences at constant impact energy are considered in order to investigate behavior of composite structures. The experimental test series showed an increased energy absorption for the composite plates made with phenolic resin. Visual inspections showed a large extent of damage were observed on the polyester and epoxy resins plates when they are compared with same plates made with phenolic resin. Moreover, the effect of the carbon fiber plies location for the mixed plates was not exceptionally pronounced. It is also concluded from the experiments that the fiber orientation angle and thickness have little effect on resultant absorbed energy. The results that we captured from the current work motivates us to further examine the samples in the future works in order to determine the damage morphology under scanning electron microscopy. Moreover, the results from this study will help the authors in the future work in designing composite laminated plates having better impact resistance. The results will allow a more methodical approach in selecting the parameters to vary in order to achieve better impact performance of composite laminates against the low velocity impact loadings.

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